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CHARLES DICKENS AS A FAUNDER OF CHRISTMAS GENRE IN BRITISH LITERATURE

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ANNOTATION

"A Christmas Carol," written by Charles Dickens in late 1843, was the first Christmas book and is considered the great Christmas myth of modern literature. Dickens' attachment to Christmas in his family life and writings contributed to his popularity. The Carol entered the general consciousness, inspiring further Christmas books, essays, and stories annually from 1847 to 1867. Dickens was a multifaceted individual, excelling in various roles such as an after-dinner speaker, shorthand reporter, amateur actor, and periodical editor. He had a prodigality of life, with a brilliant mind and smart appearance. Dickens was also known for his philanthropic efforts, including directing a reformatory home for young female delinquents and engaging in charitable activities. His novels, like Bleak House and Little Dorrit, presented a somber picture of contemporary society.

Key words: book, essays, novels, editor, known.

A Christmas Carol, written in late 1843, was the first Christmas book and the one great Christmas myth of modern literature. It was the first Christmas book to be created by Charles Dickens, who later referred to his life as "Christmas philosophy." His attachment to Christmas in his family life and writings contributed to his popularity. The Carol entered the general consciousness, and further Christmas books, essays, and stories followed annually from 1847 to 1867. None equalled the Carol in potency, but some achieved great immediate popularity. Dickens was a product of his age, mixing extensively in society and continually influencing his age. He was considered the best after-dinner speaker, shorthand reporter, amateur actor, periodical editor, and dramatic recitalist. His extraliterary skills and interests were not irrelevant to his fiction.

In his early years, Dickens was both domestic and social, loving home and family life. He was a proud and efficient householder and a devoted father to his children. Dickens lived in London, entertaining many friends, including popular authors, journalists, actors, and artists. He was on friendly terms with most fellow authors and enjoyed unpretentious society. Dickens had a prodigality of life, with his brilliance of eyes and smart appearance. He was proud of his art and devoted to improving it, but had no desire to be narrowly literary. He was founder-editor of the Daily News in 1846, but his return to daily journalism proved a mistake. He directed a reformatory home for young female delinquents for over a decade, financed by his wealthy friend Angela Burdett-Coutts. His benevolent spirit found practical expression in public speeches, fund-raising activities, and private acts of charity. Dickens's novels, Bleak House, Hard Times, and Little Dorrit, were darker than their predecessors, presenting a remarkably inclusive and increasingly sombre picture of contemporary society. His imagination transformed their topicalities into an artistically coherent vision that transcended their immediate historical context.

Kathleen Tillotson praised Dickens' lifelong love-affair with his reading public, which took a new form during his separation from his wife. Dickens valued the public's affection as a stimulus to his creativity and a condition for his commercial success. He had been toying with the idea of turning paid reader since 1853, when he began giving occasional readings in aid of charity. The paid series began in April 1858, drawing on his remarkable histrionic talents, love of theatricals, and the eminently performable nature of his fiction.

Dickens' initial repertoire consisted entirely of Christmas books but was soon amplified by episodes from the novels and magazine Christmas stories. A performance usually consisted of two items, with the most popular being "The Trial from Pickwick" and the Carol. Comedy predominated, but pathos was important in the repertoire. The last reading he devised, "Sikes and Nancy," derived from Oliver Twist, introduced horrors that petrified his audiences and half killed himself. Dickens was a magnificent performer, demonstrating important elements in his art through his oral and dramatic qualities. His insight and skill revealed nuances in narration and characterization that few readers had noticed. However, such extracts or short stories excluded some of his larger and deeper effects, notably his social criticism and analysis.

Dickens enjoyed the experience until near the end, becoming ill and exhausted. He was writing much less in the 1860s, possibly because the readings exhausted his energies while providing the income, creative satisfaction, and continuous contact with an audience he had previously obtained through the novels. He gloried in his audiences'

admiration and love, but some friends considered this too crude a gratification and a sad declension into a lesser and ephemeral art.

Ralph Waldo Emerson, during a reading of Charles Dickens, was initially skeptical of his genius due to his numerous talents beyond his imagination. However, after discussing Dickens with Emerson, he realized that there is no simple key to his prolific and multifarious nature. Dickens's fiction is related to his practical, journalistic, oratorical, and histrionic talents, as well as his concern for social evils and the limitations of humanity. His novels cover a wide range of social, moral, emotional, and psychological issues, addressing both ordinary people and abnormality. Biographers have only explored Dickens's complexity since the mid-20th century. Critics have always been challenged by his art, but from the start, it contained enough easily acceptable ingredients and evident skill to ensure popularity. The earlier novels, such as *The Pickwick Papers*, *Oliver Twist*, *Martin Chuzzlewit*, *A Christmas Carol*, and *David Copperfield*, were his most popular works throughout the 20th century. However, critics began to demur against later novels, deploring the loss of the freer comic spirit and the more symbolic mode of his art. Dickens was not neglected or forgotten, but for 70 years after his death, he received remarkably little serious attention. F.R. Leavis, later to revise his opinion, asserted that the adult mind doesn't generally find in Dickens a challenge to an unusual and sustained seriousness.

"Modern" Dickens criticism dates from 1940-41, with different impulses given by George Orwell, Edmund Wilson, and Humphry House. In the 1950s, a substantial reassessment and re-editing of his works began, finding his finest artistry and greatest depth in *Bleak House*, *Little Dorrit*, and *Great Expectations*. During the second half of the 20th century, scholars explored Dickens's working methods, relations with his public, and his standing as a Victorian figure and author for all time. At the turn of the 21st century, Dickens remained a compelling figure for biographers, scholars, television and film producers, and everyday readers.

Christmas Carol is a novella by Charles Dickens, first published in London in 1843. It tells the story of Ebenezer Scrooge, an elderly miser, who is visited by the ghost of his former business partner Jacob Marley and the spirits of Christmas Past, Present, and Yet to Come. The story is influenced by Dickens' own youth experiences and the Christmas stories of other authors, such as Washington Irving and Douglas Jerrold. The novella explores themes of the poor treatment of the poor and the ability of a selfish man to redeem himself. The story has been adapted for film, stage, opera, and other media.

Dickens wrote *A Christmas Carol* during a period when the British were exploring and reevaluating past Christmas traditions. The story was illicitly copied in

January 1844, and Dickens took legal action against the publishers, who went bankrupt. He subsequently wrote four other Christmas stories and began public readings of the story in 1849, which proved successful. A Christmas Carol has never been out of print and has been translated into several languages. It captured the zeitgeist of the early Victorian revival of the Christmas holiday and later inspired aspects of Christmas, including family gatherings, seasonal food and drink, dancing, games, and a festive generosity of spirit.

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